

1 *Original Article*2 **Outcome of open spinal surgery for decompression for the treatment of severe lumbar canal stenosis**
3 **in a neurosurgical unit in Kaduna.**4
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10 * Correspondence: doplass@yahoo.com ; Tel.: +2348069432297 (Danjuma Sale)11 **Abstract:**12 *Background*13 *Lumbar canal stenosis (LCS) is commonly seen with advancing age. In most cases decompression via laminectomy, discectomy,*
14 *foraminotomy and stabilization is the standard of care for this condition. It has advanced from open to minimally invasive*
15 *approaches. In our practice the minimally invasive approach is not yet readily available and affordable.*16 *The aim of this study is to assess outcome of patients based on the change in visual analog score following open laminectomy for*
17 *severe lumbar canal stenosis in our practice.*18 *Materials and method*19 *This is a prospective study involving patients with lumbar canal stenosis presenting at a neurosurgical unit in Kaduna. All*
20 *patients with severe symptoms who consented to open laminectomy were included in the study. Epidemiological, clinical and*
21 *radiological data was obtained using a proforma. The Visual analogue score (VAS) was used to assess the severity of pain. The*
22 *VAS was recorded at first contact (VAS-1), then at discharge (VAS-2) and at 6-month (VAS-3). The differences in the VAS were*
23 *considered as primary outcome measure. Secondary outcome measures included post-operative complication and improvement of*
24 *other symptoms.*25 *The data obtained was analyzed using SPSS version 25 for windows.*26 **Citation:** Authors First and Initials

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Results

A total of 27 patients were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 54.8 years. Presenting symptoms included lower back pain, neurogenic claudication and radiculopathy in most patients. The most common level of lumbar canal stenosis was L4 to L5.

The mean VAS-1, VAS-2 and VAS-3 were 8.7, 1.9 and 1.2 with standard deviation of 1.0, 1.3 and 0.8 respectively. The observed differences in mean between VAS-1 and VAS-2 and VAS-1 and VAS-3 were statistically significant. Significant improvement in their claudication distance was seen at 1-year of follow up in 95.2%. One patient had CSF leak with consequent surgical site infection.

Conclusions

Open surgery for decompression leads to improve in the clinical outcome as measured by the visual analog scale.

38 *Keywords: Degenerative, neurogenic claudication, surgery, visual analog score, back pain*

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41 **1. Introduction**

42 Lumbar canal stenosis (LCS) is commonly seen with advancing age.¹⁻⁴ This is as a result of narrowing of the canal as
43 a result of degenerative changes occurring in the facet joints, ligamentum flavum hypertrophy, disc degeneration with
44 formation of osteophytes.^{1,3} This in turn leads to spinal cord and/or nerve root compression depending on the level.⁴
45 Many patients with lumbar stenosis are asymptomatic, those with at least 50 % reduction in canal width often
46 manifest symptoms.^{5,6} The main symptoms are low back pain radiating to the lower limbs worsened by walking and
47 numbness in the legs.^{1,8} . The majority of patients with symptomatic lumbar stenosis can be managed conservatively
48 with drugs, weight reduction, physical therapy, and epidural steroid injections.^{9,10} However, surgery may become
49 inevitable when the symptoms become severe and not responding to non-operative measures.^{1,3}
50 Surgery for decompression and stabilization if there is instability is the standard of care for this condition if non-
51 operative treatment measures failed.¹⁰ It has advanced from open to minimally invasive approaches. In our practice
52 the minimally invasive approach is not yet readily available. Where it is available the cost is usually too high for the
53 patients to afford.

54 The aim of the study is to assess outcome of patients based on change in the Visual Analog Score who had open spinal
55 surgery for lumbar canal stenosis in our practice.

56

57 **Materials and methods**

58 Study design.

59 This is a prospective study involving patients with lumbar canal stenosis presenting at a neurosurgical unit in Kaduna
60

61 Study population:

62 The neurosurgical unit is located in Kaduna City North western Nigeria. Kaduna City has a population of about 4
63 million. Unit serves many hospitals within the city and also gets referral from outside the city.

64 Inclusion criteria: All patients with severe symptoms which was defined as a VAS score of 5 and above and was not
65 controlled by non-operative measures, who consented to open laminectomy were included in the study.

66

67 Exclusion criteria: all patients who opted for non-operative treatment and those who could not afford the procedure
68 were excluded. In addition, patients who decided on minimally invasive approach were excluded from this study.

69

70 Data collection: The data was collected using a proforma. Epidemiological and clinical data was obtained. The level of
71 stenosis was recorded. The surgery was done under general anaesthesia in the prone position. Decompression was
72 achieved by a combination of one or more of the following; laminectomy, discectomy, removal of hypertrophied
73 ligamentum flavum until the nerve roots cord and/or the nerve roots are free.

74 The Visual analogue score was used to assess the severity of pain. The VAS was recorded at first contact, then at
75 discharge and at 6-month and 1-year of follow up.

76 The differences in the VAS were considered as primary outcome measure. Secondary outcome measures included;
77 surgical site infection, post-operative cerebrospinal fluid leakage and improvement in the claudication distance at 1
78 year follow up.

79 **Data Analysis:** The data obtained was analyzed using SPSS version 25 for windows. Descriptive statistic was done for
 80 clinical and demographic variables. The differences between mean of VAS were compared using paired t-test. The
 81 confidence level was set at 95%.

82 **Ethical Considerations:** all participants signed written informed consent for the study. The study was approved by the
 83 ethic and research committee of the hospital.

84
 85 **Results**

86 A total of 27 patients were included in the study. The male female ratio was 1:1.45. The age of participants ranged
 87 from 38 to 67 years with a mean of 54.8 years and standard deviation of 8.2 years.

88 The most common presenting symptom was lower back pain. This was present in all the patients. Neurogenic
 89 claudication was present in 77.8% of the patients and radiculopathy in 37%. Other symptoms are shown on Table 1
 90

91 Table 1: Symptoms of Lumbar Canal stenosis

Symptoms	Frequency	percentage
Lower back pain	27	100
Neurogenic claudication	21	77.8
Radiculopathy	10	37
Numbness	8	29.6
Limb weakness	7	25.9
Erectile dysfunctions	3	11.1

92
 93 The most common level of lumbar canal stenosis was L4 to L5. Others are shown on Table 2.
 94

Table 2: Spinal Level of Lumbar canal stenosis

Lumbar Spinal Level	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	2	7.4
2-3	5	18.5
2-4	1	3.7
3-3	1	3.7
3-4	2	7.4
3-5	1	3.7
4-5	15	55.6
Total	27	100.0

95 The mean VAS-1, VAS-2 and VAS-3 were 8.7, 1.9 and 1.2 with standard deviation of 1.0, 1.3 and 0.8 respectively.
 96 There is weak but positive correlation between the pairs; VAS-1 and VAS-2; VAS-1 and VAS-3 and VAS-2 and VAS-3
 97 with Pearson correlation of 0.95, 0.314 and 0.278 respectively.

98
 99 The observed differences in mean between VAS-1 and VAS-2 and VAS -1 and VAS-3 were statistically significance.
 100 (p<0.001). However, observed differences between VAS-2 and VAS-3 were not statistically significant. (p>0.001). See
 101 table 3

102 Table 3: Paired Samples Test
 103

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	VAS1 - VAS2	6.741	1.583	.305	6.114	7.367	22.121	26	.000
Pair 2	VAS1 - VAS3	7.481	1.087	.209	7.051	7.912	35.752	26	.000
Pair 3	VAS2 - VAS3	.741	1.318	.254	.219	1.262	2.920	26	.007

104

105 Significant improvement in their claudication distance was seen at 1-year of follow up in 95.2% of the 21 patients who
 106 had neurogenic claudication. One patient had CSF leak and when ahead to developed deep incisional surgical site
 107 infection.

108

109 **Discussions**

110 Lumbar canal stenosis is common with increasing age and is one of the common causes of morbidity leading to lower
 111 back pain and restrain in activity of daily living. Lumbar canal stenosis remains a common disorder in the ever-
 112 increasing aging population, and surgical treatment can benefit patients for whom conservative treatment methods
 113 have failed.⁸ In this study lumbar, the mean age is 54.8 years. This finding is consistent with findings in other places
 114 where patients with degenerative causes are generally at least 50 years old although traumatic and congenital causes
 115 may occur ealier.^{1-4,9}

116

117 The most common level of canal stenosis in the lumbar region was L4 to L5, followed by L3/L4. This finding is similar
 118 to findings in other places. These two-motion segment are commonly affected by degenerative process.¹¹ Both are in
 119 transition from the mobile Lumbar segment to the more rigid sacral segment. In addition, they are more prone to
 120 rotatory strains due the less sagittal orientation of their posterior joints.¹¹

121 There is significant improvement following open laminectomy with reduction of symptoms and improvement the
 122 claudication distance

123 CSF leakage with consequent surgical site infection occurred in one patient. This led to prolonged hospitalization.

124

125 **Conclusions**

126 Open surgery for decompression leads to improve in the clinical outcome as measured by the visual analog scale. It
 127 will remain an option for carefully selected patients who cannot afford minimally invasive procedures

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